

ART FRONTIER

An International Art Journal / Vol.3 No.1 Jan.-Mar. 2025

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To cite this article: Fengyi (Jeffrey) Jiang, "Ethics In War Photojournalism and the Moral Issue of Photojournalists," *Art Frontier* 3, no.1 (March 2025): -, <https://doi.org/10.64212/CJHU2953>.

DOI: 10.64212/CJHU2953

ISSN: 2835-5490

EISSN: 2836-841X

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This article has undergone double-blind peer review.

Website: www.artfrontier.org

Email: artfrontier2023@outlook.com

Publishing Frequency: Quarterly (March, June, September, December)

Ethics In War Photojournalism and the Moral Issue of Photojournalists

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Abstract

This is a documentary war photograph taken by war photographer David Turnley, a colleague of renowned war photographer James Nachtwey. The image shows Nachtwey raising his camera to capture a scene of one teenager holding a firearm amid chaos. The photo was taken in Thokoza, South Africa, in 1994, during intense civil conflict between the African National Congress (ANC) and the Inkatha Freedom Party (IFP). The photograph is also connected to the broader context of the 1994 Rwandan Genocide. This photograph has sparked profound discussions on the ethics of war photography: while revealing the harsh reality, how should photographers safeguard the dignity of vulnerable groups such as children? This photographer attempts to convey educational messages while respecting the informed consent, privacy rights of the subjects, and avoiding secondary harm. However, some critics argue that although such works aim to present the reality, they may inadvertently reinforce the negative stereotype of African teenager as “naturally violent.” The responsibility of war photography should be to inspire society and evoke reflection, rather than using the suffering of the subjects to gain attention. The photographer endeavors to photograph children in an ethical and non - intrusive manner. Nevertheless, photojournalists constantly face a moral dilemma: revealing the truth may violate an individual’s right to privacy. This tension not only tests the ethical boundaries of photographers but also prompts viewers to look beyond the surface of the images. When we view such photographs from a critical perspective, they have the potential to inspire empathy and in - depth reflection—provided that viewers approach the images with care rather than consuming them as “spectacles” for sensationalism.

Key Words

War photography, art and politics, image dissemination, photography ethics, documentary photography

1. History & Preview

Famous war photographer James Nachtwey’s colleague, David Turnley, captured a shocking photo during the 1994 Rwandan Genocide. The photo depicts a conflict between supporters of the African National Congress (ANC) and Zulu miners in a small town in the East Rand region of South Africa, just before the country's first free elections. The photograph captures a child wielding a steel gun in the midst of chaotic streets, with war photographer James Nachtwey in the background raising his camera to capture this harrowing moment.

During the span of 100 days, brutally murdered an estimated 900,000 people, women, and children of the Tutsi ethnic group. The genocide was marked by widespread atrocities, including mass killings and the use of deadly weapons to commit mass murder. The aftermath of the genocide left the country in ruins, with millions of citizens killed or displaced. This picture highlights the daunting horrors that victims faced during this time period. The photograph’s key subject is a young teenager, dressed in a typical youth outfit of jeans, a nice shirt, and sneakers, holding an assault rifle. In the photo, the boy is slightly hunched over, clearly in

Figure 1. James Nachtwey, in Thokozza, South Africa, 1994 in a running street battle during a civil war between the ANC and Inkhata. Photo by David Turnley.

active pursuit of either defending himself or of an enemy to fight. Although he faces away from the camera, it is clear to viewers that he is holding a large weapon, a military-grade assault rifle. He looks young, wearing blue jeans, sneakers, and a clean shirt. Around him, a group of horrified people hide from nearby violence while multiple photographers capture his image from multiple sides. The boy's calm yet active stance illustrates muscle tension that indicates that he likely participates in the violence around him regularly. The photographer uses the angle of the photo to hide the teenager's facial expressions, which characterizes the teenager's backstory as more mysterious to the audience. Equally striking is the image of the photojournalists sitting in the midst of the violent scene. Not only are they close to the teenager in the photo, but they are also in range to others with deadly weapons. They appear unbothered and focused solely on their task of photographing the event. This image contrasts a typical young teenager's lifestyle with prevailing educational and social opportunities rather than holding such deadly weapons while trying to survive such a hostile environment. In the background of the photo,

many civilians lay on the ground, presumably to shield themselves from stray bullets or because they are injured themselves. This photo has become so noteworthy because it captures a candid moment during a horrific time period: it illustrates both the violence of the setting and the lengths to which photojournalists go in order to tell a story. While they are in charge of documenting global events, they cannot effectively capture these moments as mere bystanders. Sometimes, they must shockingly risk their lives in order to achieve their art while also publicizing populations in their worst and most vulnerable moments. This trend begs the question: to what extent is it ethical for photojournalists to capture scenes of war?

2. Ethics & War Photojournalism

Before exploring the connection between ethics and photojournalism, the most fundamental question is how to define "ethics." Though most people think of ethics as a set of rules identifying the rights or the wrongs, ancient philosopher Confucius defines ethics as,

“norms for conduct that distinguish between acceptable and unacceptable behavior” (National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences). Modern bloggers tend to understand ethics as “...the study of how people behave and how they should behave toward other persons, sentient beings... and systems...” (Lester). Lester believes ethics is a form of philosophy that deals with the question of whether something is right or wrong.

War photojournalism evokes severe ethical concerns towards the photojournalists and the subjects they work to capture. One of the key issues that arises during photojournalistic work sessions is the dilemma to intervene or witness and photograph the situations as bystanders. When the photographers choose to simply remain witnesses, they can capture the most authentic moments, which help draw global attention to the crises in the frame. However, not intervening to help those desperate subjects raises moral questions for photojournalists. This photograph captures the street scene during the South African massacre with clear intentions to raise global awareness about the genocide in Rwanda. However, even with the harmless intention of simply capturing live events as a war photojournalist, individuals like the subject in the photo may feel threatened and vulnerable with so many journalists around them.

Subjects of photos taken by war photojournalists, like this teenager in this publicly released photo, may also feel violated by the global exposure of their nation's suffering. The ethical concerns of the nationwide broadcasts are a result of the photographer's power to share these images globally, while the subject has no control over what happens to them over their image. In capturing an event in a certain way, the photographer can make political, social, or economic statements in order to generate a specific reaction from an audience without the subject's control or consent. These messages have the potential to change public perception or even to alter public policies. However, one noteworthy observation is that photojournalism is presumably respectful, leaving the teenager with an anonymous identity by not showing his face to the public. Photojournalists like Nachtway promote ethical photography by promoting powerful emotions without harming or stereotyping his subjects.

American writer Susan Sontag defines photography as “one's ability to appropriate the (subject) photographed. It feels like putting oneself into relation with the world that feels like knowledge.” (Sontag, *On Photography* 2). Considering Sontag's definition, the war photographer David Turnley provided enough anonymity to his subjects, while also identifying with him as an

individual. The subject of this photograph is in the center of the shot. It is clear that the photographer's focus is on this one person in the midst of a chaotic war scene. Even without dialogue, captions, or the subject's face, the war photographer David Turnley supports Sontag's assertion that a good photographer lets the audience know the subject. In order to convey the harsh reality of war, the war photographer presents the situation of the Rwanda Genocide from the context of civilians caught in the action in order to prevent misinterpretation. In his article “What Are Ethics,” Lester claims, “As long as you attempt or accomplish the unique role-related responsibilities that define your position, whether personal or professional, and any injury you may cause to another while performing those duties can be justified, you are most likely acting ethically” (Lester). Based on Lester's claim, David Turnley's photo illustrates at least one definition of ethical photojournalism. His “position” as a photographer is to report on a dangerous event without interfering or causing injury. While he is in close proximity to the events, he does not seem to be in the way of any of the soldiers. Also, he shoots the photo from behind, so the subject maintains his anonymity, thus not causing harm or injury to the teenage boy's future. Evidence connecting Lester's justification of his photojournalistic role illustrates David Turnley's ethical method of providing information to the world.

3. Critical Ethics Concerns

Ethical issues can arise when the subject of photography is or feels violated during the process of photojournalism. For example, survivors of the Rwandan Genocide may feel retraumatized by the media's photographic revelation of their agonization. In essence, in order to be ethical, the photographs taken during a war must not interfere, cause injury, or serve no purpose. If they function solely for entertainment or monetary gain without accurately portraying world events for the sake of historical or political benefit, they may be unethical.

According to “The Importance and Consequences of War Photography,” “photographs are trusted by our readers to be an accurate recording of an event.” (Jonisova). Photojournalism's goal is to provide the audience with the true recordings of situations in conflict, yet there are photographic actions journalists utilize that can alter the viewers' perception of otherwise true events. This photograph depicts the street scene during the civil war in Kosovo, South Africa, two photojournalists are visible in front of the teenager

holding a rifle, appearing to coach him. In order to capture the close-up image of the teenager, these photographers went through such extreme actions in order to create the image they wanted to portray in the media. They crouch in a certain place, find their subjects, and shoot in a way to capture exactly what they want the world to see. The nature of photography is that it is a still image, so it is nearly impossible for the viewer to decipher what is real and what is a coached illusion... This approach can raise ethical concerns about the journalists' exploitation of their subjects at their most vulnerable, particularly as they photograph teenage soldiers and others in distress without explicit consent. Although photojournalists strive for objectivity, their presence can directly or indirectly influence the events they are documenting. It is possible for the photographer to cause accidental interference, to alter the motivations of the people involved, or to cause emotional damage to participants in the event. The proximity between the photojournalists and the subject can also become a significant ethical responsibility. The two unidentified photographers on the ground with bulky cameras could affect the teenagers' conflict by giving away his position. They have also invaded the teens' personal space, which may alter his ability to effectively defend himself or to worsen the traumas suffered by those photographed. As Sontag reminds the public, "Photographing is essentially an act of non-intervention" (Sontag). Non-intervention means staying on the sidelines, not becoming involved in a conflict, and not interacting with the subjects. Just as an animal photographer does not intervene when a lion attacks and kills an antelope, a photojournalist should not intervene to aid or detract from either side of a conflict in war. While Nachtway did not seem to intervene with the teenager in his photograph, the full impact is unclear without a series of images that details what happens before or after the photo is taken. Thus, photojournalists should recognize that by taking a photo, the act of non-intervention is what needs to be found. There are other issues that contain photojournalists focusing narrowly on a single subject. For example, certain photographs can fail to capture the context of a moment, leading to a skewed representation of events. Sontag explains how this behavior can misinform the audience and their understanding since "photographs furnish evidence. Something we hear about, but doubt seems proven when we're shown a photograph of it" (Sontag). Sontag's philosophy on photojournalism suggests that, especially in the case of Nachtway's piece, photojournalists surrounding the teenager often ignore the consequence of showing "Accuracy, truthfulness, and objectivity. Those are three main conditions that

war photography must meet according to the journalism code of ethics" (Lábová & Láb, 2009: 135)" (Jonisova). Nachtway's photo is from a close viewpoint, which skews the entire moment. The viewer is unable to see the target of gun violence, how many soldiers and civilians are involved in the entire conflict, and any moments that precede or follow this initial photograph. As such, it may not be completely objective because it is missing parts of the story. The mainframe of war photojournalism is to provide truthful information and photographic evidence for audiences around the world. The framing and context of each war photograph can influence how the public perceives them. The absence of context or background information can lead to misinterpretation or oversimplification of complex situations. For example, this picture shot can obtain unique perspectives based on the techniques Nachtway uses. His perspective and his vantage point tell a story that is potentially inaccurate.

4. Stereotypes & Misconceptions

Misconceptions and stereotypes have been tools to sway public opinion to believe simple truths about large groups of people, events, or locations. Certain misconceptions mislead the public. One example is that all "African Americans are criminals.... As with the printing term from which the word comes, stereotype is a shorthand way to describe a person with collective, rather than unique characteristics. Visual stereotypes are easily found in all manner of media, but not easily defended" (Lester). Stereotyping is another major concern of photojournalism, as exemplified by David Turnley's image, revolving around the potential racial stereotyping against the subject of the image. In this case, one of the primary stereotyping issues in media portrayal is the depiction of African youth as dangerous soldiers holding violent weapons often affiliated with the cause of mass murders. This can exacerbate the paradigm that Africans are often involved in violence, ignoring the complex socio-political factors that lead to those situations. In David Turnley's photo, many perspectives could lead to different interpretations of the stereotype. His target audience was American citizens, and his main goal was to raise awareness about the horrors of the Rwandan Genocide. In hoping to convey this message, he used the teenager's experience. However, many audiences will forget to consider the perspective of the teenager. While at first glance, some might assume that he is choosing violence or acting in a criminal nature, the reasons he may be wielding the assault rifle could be trying to defend his family against rebels or enemies. The portrayal of violence and

dehumanization reduces the African community to mere symbols of conflict as shown in the photo.

The focus on the teenager holding an assault rifle simplifies the situation in the image. For example, an audience who has not fully grasped the totality of the Rwandan Genocide might not understand the significance of the photo and what it entails. This simplification of the backstories behind why teenagers are holding a rifle could easily cover up the other aspects such as political causes, international inaction, and the experiences of other victims.

5. Direct or Indirect Propaganda

Photojournalistic propaganda refers to a method in which political figures and organizations use media images to influence the decision-making skills of civilians of certain groups. These images, videos, and recollections invoke and manipulate emotions passed on by the photographer's artistic choices. Propaganda in war photojournalism can either be direct, when the intent is to persuade others using clear and explicit emotions, or it can be indirect photo propaganda, when the influence is more subtle. Direct propaganda might include an image with text, a parodied or edited photo to make a subject appear more menacing or evil, or a photo of direct wrongdoing. Indirect photographic propaganda might be more open to interpretation, perhaps in images that show a battle scene from one side, an individual committing a vague action that could be misconstrued, or an image of a political figure in a compromising location or position. Either way, it is clear that photographers can set up and edit their work in order to highlight a particular message. The ethical implications are significant, as between unbiased documentations and propagandist manipulation can often blur and impact the credibility and objectivity of an ethical photojournalistic practice.

According to Jonisova's article about photographic propaganda, "Propagandistic photography is usually taken and published with the purpose of celebrating or strengthening the established regime or destroying it" (Jonisova). Jonisova contributes to the suggestions that this photography depicts a street scene during the Kosovo War in South Africa and identifies its possible use as propagandistic photography for opposing or allied political propaganda. The robust imagery of a teenage soldier evokes strong emotional responses, potentially shaping public opinion and drawing attention to the crisis. It also acts as propaganda in their captures so that society can safely understand,

broadcast, and educate themselves about the subjects. that can manifest patriotic feelings towards a certain government. However, the photograph can also be used to frame conflict against other government parties. By focusing on the armed teenager, this image highlights the brutal reality of the state of widespread violence, which calls for humanitarian aid. While this photograph is a significant and impactful record of the Rwanda Genocide, its implication of acting as photojournalistic propaganda requires an inquiry into its ethical implications. Audiences must consider the ethics of his photo, specifically whether or not his image could accurately project the devastation that was occurring in Rwanda. Doing so would ensure that such images can be used safely for educating and broadcasting information. Photojournalists have the responsibility to be objective in their captures so that society can safely understand, broadcast, and educate themselves about the subjects.

6. Concluding the War Photojournalism & Ethics Problem

The war photographer James Nachtwey's colleague David Turnley's image evokes strong emotions throughout the world as a testament to the conflict during the Rwandan Genocide. War photojournalism can guide or uncover emotions from photos to the audience, allowing them to view different parts of the war with a simple truthful picture. However, media ethics writers like Lester answer that "Regardless of the technology employed and the underlying purpose of the media message, the five concerns of violence, privacy, manipulations, persuasion, and stereotypes should be considered as you read through the subsequent chapters and carefully study the examples and case studies provided" (Lester). Many issues concerning ethics and morale can inspire major ethical questions. How can photographers ensure that their work respects the dignity of the subjects and accurately represents the complexity of the events? Balancing the documentation of images required to spread messages about conflict in war photojournalism is still a challenge today in the field of journalism. This image, alongside many other similar photos, contains important reminders of the best way to navigate the field of ethical war photojournalism. For war photojournalism to become a widely utilized source of education, photographers must maintain a balance between intervening with subjects ethically or bearing witness to history and respecting those strangers they identify as subjects who are living through the difficult moments in a complex history that society continually

attempts to comprehend.

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Editor: Liu Ge

ENDNOTES

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戰爭新聞攝影的倫理與攝影記者的道德問題

蔣豐屹

摘要：這是由著名戰地攝影師 James Nachtwey 的同事，戰地攝影師 David Turnley 拍攝的戰地紀實照片。在這張照片中，納赫特威舉起相機，捕捉到了一個青少年在混亂中拿著槍的場景。這張照片拍攝於 1994 年南非的索科黎，當時非洲人國民大會 (ANC) 和因卡塔自由黨 (IFP) 之間發生了激烈的內戰。這張照片也與 1994 年盧旺達種族滅絕的大背景有關。這幅照片引發了關於戰爭攝影倫理的深刻討論：在揭示殘酷現實的同時，攝影師應如何維護像兒童這樣弱勢群體的尊嚴？這位攝影師試圖在傳達教育意義的同時，尊重被攝者的知情同意、隱私權以及避免二次傷害。然而，也有批評者認為，這類作品雖旨在展現現實，卻可能無意間強化了對非洲兒童“天生暴力”的負面刻板印象。戰地攝影的職責應是啟發社會、喚起反思，而非利用被攝者的苦難來博取關注。納克特韋努力以一種倫理且非侵入式的方式去拍攝兒童，但攝影記者始終面臨一種道德兩難：揭示真相，可能會侵犯個體的隱私權。這種張力不僅挑戰著攝影師的倫理底線，也促使觀者去突破圖像表層。當我們以批判性的視角觀看這類照片時，它們有潛力激發共情與深層反思——前提是觀者以關懷的態度接近影像，而非將其當作感官獵奇的“奇觀”消費。

關鍵詞：戰爭攝影；藝術政治；影像傳播；攝影倫理；紀實攝影